

A NEW SECOND DERIVATIVE BLOCK METHOD FOR SOLVING ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

Adoghe, L. O.

Department of Mathematics, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma

Corresponding Author's Email: adoghelarry@gmail.com, adolaw@aauekpoma.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

A new block hybrid second derivative method (NBHSDM) is proposed in this paper for the solution of first order initial value problem in ordinary differential equations. The method is derived using interpolation and collocation techniques of power series used as approximate solution of the initial value problems. The method consists of three methods combined to form block matrix. The analysis of the basic properties of stability and convergence of the methods were presented. Numerical examples are presented to show the efficiency and suitability for solving ODEs

Keywords: Hybrid Second derivative, Block matrix, Stiff system, A-stable, Zero-stable.

INTRODUCTION

Differential equations originates from the mathematical formulation of problems in Sciences, engineering and social sciences. Differential equations are equations involving derivative of one or more dependent variables with respect to one or more independent variables .An equation with ordinary derivative of one or more variables with respect to a single independent variable is called ordinary differential equations. Ordinary differential equations are commonly used to model problems in operation research, engineering, behavioral sciences, industrial mathematics, artificial intelligence, management and sociology (Sabo *et al.*, 2019).

An ordinary differential equation of order one with initial conditions is of the form:

$$y' = f(x, y), y(x_0) = y_0 \quad (1)$$

with $x \in [x_0, x_N]$ and $f: [x_0, x_N] \times R^m \rightarrow R^m$ is continuous and differentiable and f satisfies the Lipchitz condition (Henrici 1962).

Some of the problems that give rise to first order ordinary differential equations include the orthogonal and oblique trajectory problems, mechanics including the problems of falling body, rate problems, etc. These problems are first formulated mathematically resulting in differential equations. This formulation is called mathematical modeling. Mathematical modeling is the art of translating problem from an application area into tractable mathematical formulations whose numerical and theoretical analysis provides answers, insight and guidance useful for the originating applications. Some of the ODEs do not have closed-form solution and cannot be solved analytically hence the need to develop numerical methods to provide approximate solutions to these problems.

The general k -step LMM for the numerical solution (1) is given by

$$\sum_{j=0}^k a_j y_{n+j} = h \sum_{j=0}^k b_j y'_{n+j} \quad (2)$$

Several block multistep method have been developed to solve (1). This includes the works of Sunday *et al.* (2013), Adeyefa and Fadaka (2017).

In this present work, we shall discuss the formation of implicit Linear Multistep Method (LMM) for numerical integration of first order ODEs which are stiff.

A good numerical method for solving (1) if it is stiff must have good accuracy and reasonably wide region of absolute stability. A minimum criterion on the choice of suitable methods is that it should be A-stable. A higher order A-stable linear multistep method is obtained by carrying out modifications in two ways. These includes the use of higher derivatives and inclusion of off-grid points or hybrid points (Ezzeddine and Hojjati, 2012). Also Ijezie and Muka (2019), Hojjati *et al.* (2006), Yakubu and Markus (2016) developed other second derivatives multistep methods.

In this paper, we shall modify (2) into special one-step second derivative multistep method in which we have two off-grid points.

Some second derivative method have been derived for the solution of (1). This includes Enright (1974) who developed second derivative multistep method for solving stiff ordinary differential equations, Cash (1981) developed second derivative extended backward differentiation formula for solution of stiff systems. Also Ngwane and Jator (2012) used block hybrid second derivative method of order six to stiff systems of ODEs. Other second derivative methods developed for solving stiff systems are Adewale *et al.* (2018), Akinfenwa *et al.* (2017), Sabo *et al.* (2019). Adewale *et al.* (2017), developed second derivative method with varying step-length which is A- stable for solving stiff systems

This research work is organized as follows: in section 2, we shall discuss the derivation of the method. Section three, discusses the analysis of the methods. In section four, a few numerical problems were solved and the performance of the developed method was compared with the existing methods

Development of the Methods

The general k-step second derivative linear multistep method (SDLMM) is of the form

$$\sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j y_{n+j} = h \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j f_{n+j} + h^2 \sum_{j=0}^k \delta_j g_{n+j} \quad (3)$$

Where α_j, β_j and δ_j are real coefficients to be determined with the assumption that $\alpha_k \neq 0$. The method is said to be explicit if $\beta_k = 0, \gamma_k = 0$ and implicit if $\beta_k \neq 0, \gamma_k \neq 0$.

We shall proceed to derive our method by introducing hybrid points. Thus our method shall be a modification of (2) above and our $k = 1$

$$y(n+k) - y_n = h \sum_{j=0, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}}^k a_j f_{n+j} + h^2 g_{n+k} \quad (4)$$

Suppose the exact solution of one of (1) is $Y(x)$ in the range $[x_n, x_{n+h}]$. We shall represent the exact solution by the approximate solution of the form

$$Y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^M a_j y_j(x) \quad (5)$$

Here, the a_j 's are the coefficient to be determined and $y_j(x)$ is the polynomial basis functions of degree M , where $M = r + s$ while r and s as the number of interpolation and collocation points. We shall construct our method using $y_j(x) = x^j$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 5$. thus imposing the following conditions on (4), we have

$$Y(x) = y_n \quad (6)$$

$$Y'(x) = \sum_{j=0}^M j a_j y_j(x) = f_{n+j}, \quad j = 0, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, 1 \quad (7)$$

$$Y''(x) = \sum_{j=0}^M j(j-1) a_j y_j(x) = g_{n+j}, \quad j = 1 \quad (8)$$

where

$$g_{n+j} = \left. \frac{df(x, y(x))}{dx} \right|_{x_{n+j}, y_{n+j}}$$

Equations (5), (6) and (7) leads to a system of equations of the form

$$AX = B \quad (9)$$

Solving the above system for coefficients and substituting in (4) and after much algebraic manipulations, we obtained the following continuous scheme

$$Y(t) = a_0(t)y_n + h(b_0(t)f_n + b_1(t)f_{n+1} + b_v(t)f_{n+v}) + h^2(d_1(t)g_{n+1}) \quad (10)$$

where a_0, b_0, b_1, b_v, d_1 are the continuous coefficients given in matrix form as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{g}_0(t) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 b_0(t) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{13}{4} & \frac{29}{6} & -\frac{27}{8} & \frac{9}{10} \\ 0 & \frac{27}{4} & -\frac{63}{4} & \frac{27}{2} & -\frac{81}{20} \\ 0 & -\frac{27}{4} & \frac{45}{2} & -\frac{189}{8} & \frac{81}{10} \\ 0 & \frac{13}{4} & -\frac{139}{12} & \frac{27}{2} & -\frac{99}{20} \\ 0 & \frac{13}{4} & -\frac{139}{12} & \frac{27}{2} & -\frac{99}{20} \end{pmatrix} \\
 \dot{g}_1(t) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{11}{6} & -\frac{9}{4} & \frac{9}{10} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{11}{6} & -\frac{9}{4} & \frac{9}{10} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{11}{6} & -\frac{9}{4} & \frac{9}{10} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{11}{6} & -\frac{9}{4} & \frac{9}{10} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{11}{6} & -\frac{9}{4} & \frac{9}{10} \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

By evaluating (9) at $t = \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, 1$ and letting $v = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{2}{3}$, we have one main method and two additional methods given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} &= y_n - h \left[\frac{367}{3240} f_n + \frac{127}{1620} f_{n+1} + \frac{19}{60} f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - \frac{7}{40} f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \right] + \frac{19}{1620} h^2 g_{n+1} \\
 y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} &= y_n - h \left[\frac{43}{405} f_n + \frac{11}{405} f_{n+1} + \frac{7}{15} f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \frac{1}{15} f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \right] + \frac{2}{405} h^2 g_{n+1} \\
 y_{n+1} &= y_n - h \left[\frac{13}{120} f_n + \frac{13}{60} f_{n+1} + \frac{9}{20} f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \frac{9}{40} f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \right] + \frac{1}{60} h^2 g_{n+1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

The above methods are combined to form the block matrix defined by difference equation

$$A^{(0)} Y_a = A^{(1)} Y_{a-1} + h \dot{B}^{(0)} F_a + B^{(1)} F_{a-1} + h^2 \dot{C}^{(0)} G_a + C^{(1)} G_{a-1} \tag{12}$$

ANALYSIS OF THE BLOCK METHOD

Order and error constant

The Taylor series expansion of methods (11) above yield

$$\frac{h^j}{j!} y_n^{(j)} - y_n - \frac{h^{j+1}}{(j+1)!} y_n^{(j+1)} + \frac{367}{3240} (h)^{j-1} + \frac{19}{60} \frac{h^{j-1}}{3} - \frac{7}{40} \frac{h^{j-1}}{3} + \frac{127}{1620} (h)^{j-1} \frac{h^{j+2}}{(j+2)!} y_n^{(j+1)} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{h^{j-2}}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{h^{j-2}}{3} - \frac{19}{1620} (h)^{j-2} = 0$$

$$\frac{h^j}{j!} y_n^{(j)} - y_n - \frac{h^{j+1}}{(j+1)!} y_n^{(j+1)} + \frac{43}{405} (h)^{j-1} + \frac{7}{15} \frac{h^{j-1}}{3} - \frac{1}{15} \frac{h^{j-1}}{3} + \frac{11}{405} (h)^{j-1} \frac{h^{j+2}}{(j+2)!} y_n^{(j+1)} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{h^{j-2}}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{h^{j-2}}{3} - \frac{2}{405} (h)^{j-2} = 0$$

$$\frac{h^j}{j!} y_n^{(j)} - y_n - \frac{h^{j+1}}{(j+1)!} y_n^{(j+1)} + \frac{13}{20} (h)^{j-1} + \frac{9}{20} \frac{h^{j-1}}{3} + \frac{9}{40} \frac{h^{j-1}}{3} + \frac{13}{60} (h)^{j-1} \frac{h^{j+2}}{(j+2)!} y_n^{(j+1)} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{h^{j-2}}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{h^{j-2}}{3} - \frac{1}{60} (h)^{j-2} = 0$$

Thus the analysis of methods (10) shows they are of order $p = [5, 5, 5]^T$ with error constants given as

$$C_{p+1} = \left[\frac{97}{524880}, \frac{2}{164025}, \frac{1}{64800} \right]^T$$

Stability Analysis of Method

The block matrix finite difference form of our methods in (11) can be written as

$$A^{(0)} Y_a = A^{(1)} Y_{a-1} + h B^{(0)} F_a + B^{(1)} F_{a-1} + h^2 C^{(0)} G_a + C^{(1)} G_{a-1}$$

Where $Y_a = \begin{bmatrix} y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} \\ y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \\ y_{n+1} \end{bmatrix}$, $Y_{a-1} = \begin{bmatrix} y_{n-\frac{1}{3}} \\ y_{n-\frac{2}{3}} \\ y_n \end{bmatrix}$, $F_a = \begin{bmatrix} f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} \\ f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \\ f_{n+1} \end{bmatrix}$

$F_{a-1} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{n-\frac{1}{3}} \\ f_{n-\frac{2}{3}} \\ f_n \end{bmatrix}$, $G_a = \begin{bmatrix} g_{n+\frac{1}{3}} \\ g_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \\ g_{n+1} \end{bmatrix}$, $G_{a-1} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{n-\frac{1}{3}} \\ g_{n-\frac{2}{3}} \\ g_n \end{bmatrix}$

And $A^{(0)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, $A^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, $B^{(0)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{19}{60} & -\frac{7}{40} & \frac{127}{1620} \\ \frac{7}{15} & \frac{1}{15} & \frac{11}{405} \\ \frac{9}{20} & \frac{9}{40} & \frac{13}{60} \end{bmatrix}$

$$B^{(1)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{367}{3240} \\ 0 & \frac{43}{405} \\ 0 & \frac{13}{120} \end{pmatrix} \quad C^{(0)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{19}{1620} \\ 0 & -\frac{2}{405} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{60} \end{pmatrix} \quad C^{(1)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Zero stability of Method

The zero stability property is concerned with the stability of difference system in (14) in the limit as $h \rightarrow 0$. As $h \rightarrow 0$ (14) becomes

$$A^{(0)}Y_a - A^{(1)}Y_{a-1} = 0 \tag{15}$$

The characteristic polynomial of the above is given by

$$r(l) = \det(l A^{(0)} - A^{(1)})$$

$$\text{Thus } r(l) = \det(l A^{(0)} - A^{(1)}) = \det \begin{pmatrix} l & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = l^2(l - 1)$$

The block method (14) is zero stable since from (15); if $r(l) = 0$ satisfies $|l_i| \leq 1, i = 1, 2, 3$ and for $|l_i| = 1$, the multiplicity does not exceed 1

Consistency of Method

The method (14) is consistent as it has order $p > 1$, hence according to Henrici (1962), we can say that our method is convergent.

Linear stability

In the spirit of Brugano and Triagiante (1998); Hairer and Wanner (1996), we shall consider the following test equations

$$y' = l y, y'' = l^2 y$$

Which when applied to (14), yield

$$Y_a = M(z)Y_{a-1}, z = l h$$

Where the matrix $M(z)$ is given as

$$M(z) = (A^{(0)} - zB^{(0)} - z^2C^{(0)})^{-1} (A^{(1)} + zB^{(1)} + z^2C^{(1)}) \quad (16)$$

From (16), we shall obtain the stability polynomial $R(z)$ given as

$$R(z) = - \frac{2z^3 - 3z^2 - 99z + 540}{z^4 - 13z^3 - 69z^2 - 324z - 540} \quad (17)$$

The region of absolute stability of the method is therefore defined as

$$G = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |R(z)| \leq 1\} \quad (18)$$

The stability requirement of the method for solving stiff system is that the method is A-stable. For method (14), this can only be achieved if the left – half complex plane is contained in G. Below is the plot representing the stability region corresponding to the stability function $R(z)$ is given below

Fig. 1 Region of absolute stability of our method

Numerical Experiments

We shall consider the following problems to examine the computational efficiency and accuracy of the new method. MAPLE 18 software was used in all computations.

Problem 1

$$y' = -8y + 7z, y(0) = 1$$

$$z' = 42y - 43z, z(0) = 8$$

$$y(x) = 2e^{-x} - e^{-50x}, z(x) = 2e^{-x} + 6e^{-50x}, h = 0.1$$

Comparison of Errors in problem 1

X	Methods	Error $ y(x_n) - y_n $
5	New method	4.4069×10^{-8}
	Okuonghae <i>et al.</i> (2014)	1.5472×10^{-2}
	Ezzeddine and Hojjati (2012)	1.5476×10^{-2}
10	New method	7.3033×10^{-7}
	Okuonghae <i>et al.</i> (2014)	9.0808×10^{-2}
	Ezzeddine and Hojjati (2012)	9.0808×10^{-2}
15	New method	3.7467×10^{-7}
	Okuonghae <i>et al.</i> (2014)	6.1186×10^{-7}
	Ezzeddine and Hojjati(2012)	6.1186×10^{-7}

Problem 2

$$y_1' = 198y_1 + 199y_2, y_1(0) = 1$$

$$y_2' = -398y_1 - 399y_2, y_2(0) = -1, h = 0.1$$

Source: Sabo *et al* (2019)

Comparison of errors in our new with errors Skwame et'al (2017) and Sabo et'al (2019)

X	Error in Skwame et'al (2017) (k=3)		Error in Sabo et'al (2019) (k=2)		Error in the new method (k=1)	
	$y_1(x)$	$y_2(x)$	$y_1(x)$	$y_2(x)$	$y_1(x)$	$y_2(x)$
0.1	$2.60' 10^{-6}$	$2.60' 10^{-6}$	$2.50' 10^{-6}$	$9.05' 10^{-6}$	$4.93' 10^{-9}$	$4.93' 10^{-9}$
0.2	$2.42' 10^{-6}$	$2.42' 10^{-6}$	$2.95' 10^{-7}$	$2.81' 10^{-7}$	$8.93' 10^{-9}$	$8.93' 10^{-9}$
0.3	$1.18' 10^{-6}$	$1.18' 10^{-6}$	$4.87' 10^{-7}$	$4.33' 10^{-6}$	$1.21' 10^{-8}$	$1.21' 10^{-8}$
0.4	$3.90' 10^{-6}$	$3.90' 10^{-6}$	$4.95' 10^{-6}$	$4.83' 10^{-6}$	$1.46' 10^{-8}$	$1.46' 10^{-8}$
0.5	$5.58' 10^{-6}$	$5.58' 10^{-6}$	$6.25' 10^{-6}$	$5.84' 10^{-6}$	$1.65' 10^{-8}$	$1.65' 10^{-8}$
0.6	$3.23' 10^{-6}$	$3.23' 10^{-6}$	$6.12' 10^{-6}$	$6.02' 10^{-6}$	$1.79' 10^{-8}$	$1.79' 10^{-8}$
0.7	$4.35' 10^{-6}$	$4.35' 10^{-6}$	$6.99' 10^{-6}$	$6.66' 10^{-6}$	$1.89' 10^{-8}$	$1.89' 10^{-8}$
0.8	$3.97' 10^{-6}$	$3.97' 10^{-6}$	$6.71' 10^{-6}$	$6.73' 10^{-6}$	$1.96' 10^{-8}$	$1.96' 10^{-8}$
0.9	$3.59' 10^{-6}$	$3.59' 10^{-6}$	$7.26' 10^{-6}$	$6.98' 10^{-6}$	$1.99' 10^{-8}$	$1.99' 10^{-8}$
1.0	$4.31' 10^{-6}$	$4.31' 10^{-6}$	$6.88' 10^{-6}$	$6.82' 10^{-6}$	$2.006' 10^{-8}$	$2.006' 10^{-8}$

Problem 3

We consider the linear stiff problem

$$y' = -y + 95z, y(0) = 1, x \in [0, 1]$$

$$z' = -y - 97z, z(0) = 1$$

$$y(x) = \frac{1}{47}(95e^{-2x} - 48e^{-96x})$$

Exact solution:

$$z(x) = \frac{1}{47}(48e^{-96x} - e^{-2x})$$

Source: Abhulimen and Ukpebor (2019)

Table 3: Comparative analysis of results of problem 3

Step	x	Method	Computed sol/error $y(x)(error)$	Computed sol/error $z(x)(error)$
$\frac{1}{8}$	10	New method	0.27355004(7.6870' 10^{-0})	- 0.0028794741(8.0861' 10^{-11})
$\frac{1}{16}$	10	Abhulimen and Ukpebor(2019)	0.27354997(3.0' 10^{-8})	- 0.002879474(1.4' 10^{-9})
		Abhulimen and Otunta(2006)	0.27354656(7.8' 10^{-5})	- 0.0029794811(3.7' 10^{-5})
		BDF1	0.27355004(1.91' 10^{-9})	- 0.002879474(2.01' 10^{-9})
		BDF2	0.036994834(2.73' 10^{-1})	0.00038942(2.49' 10^{-9})
		New method	0.27355004(3.0951' 10^{-11})	- 0.002879474110(5.7053' 10^{-13})
$\frac{1}{32}$	10	Abhulimen and Ukpebor(2019)	0.27354997(3.0' 10^{-8})	- 0.002879474(1.4' 10^{-9})
		Abhulimen and Otunta(2006)	0.27354656(7.8' 10^{-5})	- 0.0029794811(3.7' 10^{-5})
		BDF1	0.27355004(1.91' 10^{-9})	- 0.002879474(2.01' 10^{-9})
		BDF2	0.036994834(2.73' 10^{-1})	0.00038942(2.49' 10^{-9})
		New method	0.27355004(7.6282' 10^{-1})	- 0.002879474112(6.6672' 10^{-13})
		Exact solution	0.273550040584643	-0.00287947410542666

Problem 4:

$$y'' + 1001y' + 1000y = 0, y(0) = 1, y'(0) = -1$$

$$y(x) = e^{-x}$$

Source: Abhulimen and Ukpebor (2019) and Adeniran and Longe(2019)

Table 4: Results of problem 4 compared with Abhulimen and Ukpebor (2019) and Adeniran and Longe (2019)

Step	X	Method	Computed sol/error $y(x)(error)$
0.1	10	Adeniran and Longe(2019)	0.367879420284596 (2.088685×10^{-8})
		New method	0.367879441122532 (4.8910×10^{-11})
0.05	10	Abhulimen and Okunuga(2008)	0.36787930(1.8×10^{-7})
		Abhulimen and Omeike(2011)	0.36787846(1.4×10^{-8})
		Abhulimen and Ukpebor(2019)	0.367879450(8.9×10^{-8})
		New method	0.367879441611164 (4.39722×10^{-10})
0.125	10	Abhulimen(2009)	0.367879442 (2.7×10^{-8})
		Abhulimen and Ukpebor(2019)	0.367879450 (6.0×10^{-8})
		New Method	0.367879440867417 ((3.04025×10^{-10})
		Exact solution	0.367879441171442

Problem 5

$$y_1' = 998y_1 + 1998y_2, y_1(0) = 1$$

$$y_2' = -999y_1 - 1999y_2, y_2(0) = 0, h = 0.1$$

$$y_1(x) = 2e^{-x} - e^{-1000x}$$

$$y_2(x) = -e^{-x} - e^{-1000x}$$

Source : Sabo et al(2019).

Comparison of errors in problem 5 using the new method with errors Skwame *et al.* (2017) and Sabo *et al.* (2019)

X	Error in Skwame et al (2017) (k=3)		Error in Sabo et al (2019) (k=2)		Error in the new method (k=1)	
	$y_1(x)$	$y_2(x)$	$y_1(x)$	$y_2(x)$	$y_1(x)$	$y_2(x)$
0.1	$5.820' 10^{-2}$	$5.83' 10^{-2}$	$3.40' 10^{-3}$	$2.90' 10^{-3}$	$1.48' 10^{-2}$	$1.48' 10^{-2}$
0.2	$4.02' 10^{-3}$	$3.95' 10^{-3}$	$5.96' 10^{-3}$	$5.93' 10^{-3}$	$2.20' 10^{-4}$	$2.20' 10^{-4}$
0.3	$9.17' 10^{-3}$	$2.16' 10^{-3}$	$3.04' 10^{-4}$	$1.60' 10^{-4}$	$2.96' 10^{-6}$	$3.31' 10^{-6}$
0.4	$7.13' 10^{-4}$	$6.26' 10^{-4}$	$1.11' 10^{-4}$	$2.34' 10^{-5}$	$4.17' 10^{-7}$	$2.33' 10^{-7}$
0.5	$1.20' 10^{-4}$	$4.22' 10^{-5}$	$2.71' 10^{-4}$	$1.35' 10^{-4}$	$4.16' 10^{-7}$	$2.08' 10^{-7}$
0.6	$2.28' 10^{-4}$	$1.57' 10^{-4}$	$9.44' 10^{-5}$	$4.74' 10^{-5}$	$4.53' 10^{-7}$	$2.26' 10^{-7}$
0.7	$1.60' 10^{-4}$	$7.77' 10^{-5}$	$2.50' 10^{-5}$	$1.25' 10^{-4}$	$4.78' 10^{-7}$	$2.39' 10^{-7}$
0.8	$1.52' 10^{-4}$	$7.67' 10^{-5}$	$1.03' 10^{-4}$	$5.14' 10^{-5}$	$4.94' 10^{-7}$	$2.47' 10^{-7}$
0.9	$1.32' 10^{-4}$	$6.78' 10^{-5}$	$2.27' 10^{-4}$	$1.14' 10^{-4}$	$5.03' 10^{-7}$	$2.51' 10^{-7}$
1.0	$1.52' 10^{-4}$	$7.60' 10^{-5}$	$1.05' 10^{-4}$	$5.25' 10^{-5}$	$5.06' 10^{-7}$	$2.53' 10^{-7}$

Problem 6 (SIR MODEL)

The SIR model is an epidemiological model that computes the theoretical number of people infected with a contagious illness in a closed population over time. The name of this class of models derives from the fact that they involve coupled equations relating the number of susceptible people $S(t)$, number of people infected $I(t)$, and the number of people who have recovered $R(t)$. This is a good and simple model for many infectious diseases including measles, mump sand rubella. It is given by these three coupled equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dS}{dt} = m(1 - S) - bIS \\ \frac{dI}{dt} = mI - gI + bIS \\ \frac{dR}{dt} = -mR + gI \end{cases}$$

Where n, g, b are positive parameters to be determined.

Define y by

$$y = S + I + R$$

and adding the equations in (16) above, we obtain the following evolution equation for y,

$$y' = m(1 - y)$$

If we take $m = 0.5$ and the initial condition to be for a particular closed population, we have that the equation becomes

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = 0.5(1 - y), y(0) = 0.5$$

The exact solution of the above is $y(t) = 1 - 0.5e^{-0.5t}$

Source: (Sunday *et al*, 2013)

Table 6: Comparison of errors in problem 6 with errors in the method Sunday *et al*, 2013

X		Computed solution	Error in Sunday et al (2013)	Error in our method
0.1	0.52438528774964299546	0.52438528774975509975	5.574430×10^{-12}	1.12104×10^{-13}
0.2	0.54758129098202021342	0.54758129098223348722	3.946177×10^{-12}	2.1327×10^{-13}
0.3	0.56964601178747109638	0.56964601178777540486	8.183232×10^{-12}	3.0430×10^{-13}
0.4	0.59063462346100907066	0.59063462346139502690	3.436118×10^{-11}	3.8595×10^{-13}
0.5	0.61059960846429756588	0.61059960846475648204	1.929473×10^{-10}	4.5891×10^{-13}
0.6	0.62959088965914106696	0.62959088965966490843	1.879040×10^{-10}	5.2384×10^{-13}
0.7	0.64765595514064328282	0.64765595514122462514	1.776835×10^{-10}	5.8134×10^{-13}
0.8	0.66483997698218034963	0.66483997698281233810	1.724676×10^{-10}	6.3198×10^{-13}
0.9	0.68118592418911335343	0.68118592418978966521	1.847545×10^{-10}	6.7631×10^{-13}
1.0	0.69673467014368328820	0.69673467014439809672	3.005770×10^{-10}	7.1480×10^{-13}

CONCLUSION

A new block hybrid second derivative method has been developed. The method is found to have good stability properties appropriate for solving stiff systems. The accuracy of the method has been tested on some stiff systems. The method was also tested on an SIR model. The results show that the method is efficient and compared favorably with some existing methods in the literature.

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